

Affects of Product, Trust, Price and Customer Satisfaction in E-commerce Environment

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Abstract:

The exponentially development of the Internet, World Wide Web, and Electronic Commerce has altered the innovative techniques of selling and marketing about services and products. At the same time as consequences of improvement and the evolution of the electronic information assets of product and service sellers and service providers face countless novel challenges. In this research researchers have discovered major ingredients related to Product, Trust, Price and customer satisfaction in E-commerce Environment and recommended conceptual framework with the support of relationship of dependent and independents variable. Moreover Research has found that peoples who have more trust in electronic commerce they mostly involve themselves in e-commerce. In this paper researcher has collect data through questionnaire from more than 300 users and analyze data with the help of SPSS software.

Keywords: Product, price, service, website quality, Customer satisfaction and trust.

1 INTRODUCTION

Now a day's the use of internet is increasing, internet is not limited for those computer nerds who used it for entertainment or eagerness. Internet launched great opportunities to business for their users. Internet has been playing vital role for organization or customer in e-commerce (Alemayehu Molla 2001) to sell, trade, distribute products and provide services to the organizations or customers. An organization also trade with organizations and customers can trade with customers. Because of Internet e-commerce has got opportunities to business. Online businesses (Lashari 2013) appropriate/share organization data, keeping up administration connections, and directing trade exchanges by technique for telecommunications systems. E-commerce incorporates the offer purchase connections and exchanges encompassing by organizations, as unmistakably as the corporate procedures that bolster the business inside segregated firms. Presently days, the competition among online retailers has turned out to be more concentrated. Subsequently, more organizations are attempting to increase benefits by using electronic commerce to take up with customers. Along these lines, individuals turn out to be more educated about ideal costs when looking for product and services. To balance value straightforwardness disservice contenders have used three essential methodologies: geographic separation, benefit quality contrasts, and unobtrusive level of exchanging expenses. Then again, by building up the web based shopping some comprehended costs has diminished for dome customers. To put it plainly, the significance of service quality separation, in pulling in and holding customers has progressed.

Now a day's business has moved their attention from sales and products to consumer oriented promotion. However, comprehension consumers have turned out to be more imperative issue of showcasing due to the hard state of competition in the commercial center. Furthermore creating activity and procedure to give customers what they truly need and want.

During the most recent four decades, satisfaction has been considered as the most imperative hypothetical and also reasonable issues for most marketers and customer analysts. The fundamental problem in the execution of predictable online infrastructure is consumer loyalty (Intzar Ali Lashari 2013). An expansive meaning of satisfaction is that it is an enthusiastic reaction to the utilization of service and product. It is the same as an intricate human being development, which includes intellectual and full of feeling procedures. However, quality is the way to quantifying customer satisfaction. In such a way analysts have given careful reflections to the comfortable relationship between consumer loyalty and quality.

2. CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: PRODUCT, PRICE, SERVICE & SUPPORT SYSTEM, WEBSITE, TRUST.

Customarily, Satisfaction has been conceptualized as an item related information judgment that takes after a buy demonstration or a progression of utilization encounters. At the end of the day, Satisfaction is characterized as an assessment of product and service encounter. Satisfaction can be grouped in two ways: general satisfaction and transaction satisfaction. General satisfaction implies that a client's assessment of a brand depends on their past experience. Transaction satisfaction alludes the evaluation of a customer coming about because of a particular buy understanding.

PRODUCT

A huge determinant of productivity and product's market accomplishment of organizations is nature of product the prevalence of the product in measurements. The presumption is generally that if the business can't deliver great "fit and complete" products, the products won't likely have the other, more critical, quality characteristics. Nature of products impacts organizations' gainfulness and market achievement.

PRICE

The price secures products as well service. Perceived price is one mental segment that accept a basic partin customers' reaction to prices. Price can be used as a resource for growth both advantages and consumer loyalty. Demonstrated that price is a key component for customers while selecting product or service. Exactly when customers assume that product's price is sensible, the purchase direct tends to be repeated. Conversely, if customers felt like that exact product or service doesn't justify its esteem, they won't reiterate purchase direct. The outward "sensibility of price" has a helpful connection to customer care. found that price positively affects buy expectation. What's more, companies and customers differentiate the price of products and the price of same that paid by various customers and evaluate the value of price by making examinations with various references.

2.1 WEBSITE QUALITY

This research additionally concentrates on sites quality and consumer loyalty. These have been the most critical things to the association or organizations that do their business; that is working and having exchanges on the web to offer their products and services straightforwardly to their customers. Numerous associations prevail in their business by taking a shot at web based business sites in which they trust (Dan J. Kim 2009) and think with respect to the site quality, (for example, Products/services information). Along these lines, "web based business site" in this examination is characterized as the way toward offering products and services to online customers. Past inquiries about have concentrated on site quality (Eric W. Welch 2007) execution from alternate points of view, including six pointer sorts; in particular, frameworks quality, data quality, benefit quality, use, customer satisfaction (Xin Xia 2007), and advantage. Despite the fact that numerous sites improve nature of instructive, framework quality, website compositions, sympathy, and services quality to their customers, regardless they need to discover the best approach to draw in their customers and make them happy with site quality.

2.2 SERVICE AND SUPPORT

An issue of significant worth to online business services is whether their customers will come back to their webpage after their underlying background, i.e., reliability. A few variables, which impact customers' devotion need to do with the bolster the operator is equipped for giving the customer over the exchange life cycle. Clients esteem exceedingly the support and service the operator gives amid all stages (pre, amid and after-deal) of the exchange. This support and service can take diverse structures and may incorporate the accompanying: site knowledge (the degree to which the web based business framework recollects rehash customers and helps them in accomplishing objectives), pertinent inquiry offices, criticism, adding machines, currency converters, following request/shipment status, account upkeep, installment choices, FAQs, and so forth. The multifaceted experiences of customers in pre-deal, (for example, hunting down data on product and service), amid exchange and post-deal exercises and the web based business framework's capacity to support and guide the customers in every one of these stages add to the customers' satisfaction.

2.3 TRUST

Alongside the nature of the site and substance (characteristics of internet business frameworks) e-commerce utilize and fulfillment could be influenced by customers' mien towards security and protection issues. Genuine or potentially saw fears of uncovering individual data and customers' sentiments of uncertainty give special difficulties to e-commerce administrators to discover courses in which to start internet business connections. Customers are worried about the level of security present while giving touchy data on the web and will utilize online business just when they build up a specific level of trust. Trust indicates to the two imperative issues that are distinguished crosswise over studies in influencing the eventual fate of online business frameworks – security and protection. Security identifies with the insurance of data or

frameworks from unsanctioned interruptions or outpourings. Dread of the absence of security is one of the components that have been distinguished in many studies as influencing internet business development and advancement.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

On the basis of literature review 5 hypothesis are taken.

H1: Product has significantly positively influence on customer satisfaction in E-commerce.

H2: Price has significantly positive effect on customer satisfaction in E-commerce.

H3: Website has significantly positive influence on satisfaction of customers in E-commerce.

H4: Service has significantly positive influence on of customers in E-commerce.

H5: Trust has significantly positive influence on satisfaction of customers in E-commerce.

4. RESEARCHFRAMEWORK.

1. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

There are diverse sorts of methodologies for directing a research. Information asserts, Systems and strategy all add to approaches of research who has a tendency to be more qualitative, quantitative, may be both (Creswell, 2003). Then again, this project of research includes utilization of speculations; and degree to that a scientist is strong around the hypothesis toward the start of the exploration brings up a critical issue about the outline of the project of research. This research should utilize either inductive approaches or deductive approaches. Here the review of both approaches will be introduced.

Deductive Approach

In deductive approach, scholar build up the hypothesis and theory, and plan a research methodology to test the hypothesis. Reasoning accentuates logical standards, moving from hypothesis to facts, the necessity to explain fundamental connections among factors, the accumulation of information of quantitative, the use of discipline to guarantee strength of data, the working of ideas to guarantee simplicity of classification, scholar freedom of what will be explored and the need to choose tests of adequate size so as to sum up assumption.

Inductive Approach

In inductive approach, scholar would gather information and create hypothesis as an aftereffect of analysis of data. Enlistment underscores a nearby comprehension of setting of research, the accumulation of qualitative data, and an additional adaptable creation to allow research changes accentuation as the research progress, agreeing that the analyst is a part of the examination process and not as much offer by means of the necessity to sum up.

2. 4. DATA ANALYSIS

In this research data has been analyzed with SPSS and AMOS software and various techniques are used for finding reliability and co-linearity of all variables with each other. The analysis of data is thought to be the most essential portion of the research procedure. In this paper has been gathered through 300 questioners over quantitative review. After collection of data, researcher has check reliability of all variables and calculates validity of hypothesis tests. To break down the gathered information, first Method will be utilized by Cronbach's Alpha to demonstrate the questionnaire's reliability, then researchers has calculate the condition of quality of variables, and factor analysis, after factor analysis the study is conducted to find the relation between dependent variable and independents variables.

4.1 CRONBACH'S ALPHA

The reliability of variables has been checked with Cronbach's Alpha. The result of reliability test by utilizing SPSS software for the entire survey is 0.907. The base level of Cronbach's Alpha w0.7 . The reliability numbers for every variable for product, price, website quality, service, trust, as well as customer satisfaction are given in table Table 1.

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Number of items
Product	0.775	6
Price	0.789	6
Website Quality	0.788	6
Service	0.805	5
Trust	0.743	5
Satisfaction	0.722	4
All variable's total	0.948	6

Table 1

These numbers demonstrate what the proposed questionnaire's reliability is strong and it is reasonable, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.700 and all variables have more than to the base level 0.7. it is likewise reasonable in light of the fact.

The Condition of Quality Variables

The state of dependent and independents factors as to clear insights have been appeared in Table.

Table 2 One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Service	140	1.9886	.71922	.06079
Price	140	1.9964	.63330	.05352
Trust	140	2.1071	.70493	.05958
Website	140	2.0631	.66048	.05582
Product	140	2.0024	.61424	.05191
Satisfaction	140	1.9839	.65027	.05496

Condition of Quality Variables According to One-Sample T-Test

This table demonstrates the consequences of one-sample t-test. This test is utilized to survey the state of quality factors in one population.

Table 3 One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Service	32.715	139	.000	1.98857	1.8684	2.1088
price	37.300	139	.000	1.99643	1.8906	2.1023
Trust	35.368	139	.000	2.10714	1.9893	2.2249
Website	36.959	139	.000	2.06310	1.9527	2.1735
Product	38.572	139	.000	2.00238	1.8997	2.1050
Satisfaction	36.099	139	.000	1.98393	1.8753	2.0926

To discover the location of every excellence variable in research, as table shows, one sample t-test is utilized. However all the lower and upper breaking points are positive, and we can express that the state of product, price, website, service, and trust is appropriate in our model from the client's perspective.

FACTOR ANALYSIS

For every variable: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of inspecting simpleness and Bartlett's trial of sphericity; unrotated arrangement, including communalities, add up to fluctuation clarified, and part lattice.

Table 4 KMO & Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Variable	KMO Measures of Sampling Adequacy	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Approx. Chi square	Df	Sig.
Product	.795	216.062	15	.000
Price	.746	275.639	15	.000
Website	.707	337.628	15	.000
Service	.827	202.094	10	.000
Trust	.661	170.485	10	.000
Satisfaction	.799	120.618	6	.000
All variables total	.849	1065.271	15	.000

KMO is greater than 0.6 and noteworthy Bartlett's test is lesser than critical level which is 0.05, that demonstrate connection network having huge data.

Table 5 Communalities

The extraction value tells us proportion of variance for each variables explained by the factors so in this case looking at these extraction values these are very high and more than 0.50 for all the variables.

Table 6 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.795	79.912	79.912	4.795	79.912	79.912
2	.538	8.966	88.878			
3	.330	5.503	94.381			
4	.217	3.611	97.992			
5	.098	1.641	99.633			
6	.022	.367	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

This table shows the percentage of variance and cumulative percentage that is 79.912 % of all variables. Table 7Component Matrix

	Component
	1
Service	.907
Price	.903
Trust	.846
Website	.937
Product	.930
Satisfaction	.836

4.2 INFRENTIAL STATISTICS

We will test the hypothesis of research by utilizing analysis of regression by means of SPSS software. This a portion of research is done through structural equation method, in light of the fact that there are some autonomous factors that may impact the dependent variable.

Here, in light of our model of research, the consequences of theory test will be displayed in table.

REGRESION

Table 8 Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Trust, Price, Website, Service, Product	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 9 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.869 ^a	.754	.745	.32823	.754	82.314	5	134	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Product, Trust, Service, Website, price

The range of R Square which is between 0 to 1. Near to zero means it shows poor relation between independent and dependant variables. However near to 1 means stronger relation between independent and dependant variables

Table 10 Correlations

		Satisfaction	Service	price	Trust	Website	Product
Pearson Correlation	Satisfaction	1.000	.710	.611	.669	.862	.648
	Service	.710	1.000	.781	.719	.826	.818
	Price	.611	.781	1.000	.690	.766	.975
	Trust	.669	.719	.690	1.000	.758	.716
	Website	.862	.826	.766	.758	1.000	.810
	Product	.648	.818	.975	.716	.810	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Satisfaction	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Service	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	Price	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	Trust	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000

	Website	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	Product	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	Satisfaction	140	140	140	140	140	140
	Service	140	140	140	140	140	140
	Price	140	140	140	140	140	140
	Trust	140	140	140	140	140	140
	Website	140	140	140	140	140	140
	Product	140	140	140	140	140	140

Coefficient of correlation: A measures of the quality of direct relationship between two factors. It demonstrates the bearing and quality between two factors, it ranges from - 1 to +1, if the esteem is zero means there is no connection, if the esteem is close - 1 implies there is negative relationship, and if the esteem is almost 1 there is strong connection. As indicated by the table the connection between the two factors is almost 1 and more noteworthy than 0.5 it implies there is solid positive connection between the two factors.

Table 11 ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	44.340	5	8.868	82.314	.000 ^b
Residual	14.436	134	.108		
Total	58.776	139			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Product, Trust, Service, Website, price

Table 12 coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	.290	.100		2.906	.004	.093	.487
Service	.060	.078	.067	.774	.441	-.094	.214
Price	.048	.200	.047	.242	.809	-.346	.443
Trust	.063	.064	.068	.983	.328	-.063	.188
Website	.903	.088	.918	10.264	.000	.729	1.078
Product	-.259	.230	-.244	-1.123	.263	-.714	.197

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

4.3 SUMMARY OF RESULTS/FINDINGS

The purpose of this summary is to prove the hypothesis to accept/reject the hypothesis through results that we found above through SPSS software.

H1: Product will positively affect customer satisfaction in E-commerce.

Product and customer satisfaction result has proved through Cronbach's, KMO, and regression analysis and it showed the positive relationship between both variable, according to these result the hypothesis is accepted, except the value of unstandardized coefficient is negative according to this result the hypothesis is rejected.

H2: Price will positively affect customer satisfaction in E-commerce.

Price and customer satisfaction result has proved through Cronbach's, KMO, and regression analysis and it showed the positive relationship between both variable, according to these result the hypothesis is accepted.

H3: Website will positively affect satisfaction of customer in E-commerce.

Website and customer satisfaction result has proved through Cronbach's, KMO, and regression analysis and it showed the positive relationship between both variable, according to these result the hypothesis is accepted.

H4: Service will positively affect satisfaction of customer in E-commerce.

Services and customer satisfaction result has proved through Cronbach's, KMO, and regression analysis and it showed the positive relationship between both variable, according to these result the hypothesis is accepted.

H5: Trust will positively affect satisfaction of customer in E-commerce.

Trust and customer satisfaction result has proved through Cronbach's, KMO, and regression analysis and it showed the positive relationship between both variable, according to these result the hypothesis is accepted.

2 CONCLUSION

The development of the E-commerce shopping has made organizations confront numerous new difficulties in their relations with the customer to survive. Obviously during the process of an online transactions, a Website is a piece of the linking between an organization and its customer and the nonappearance of human contact must be rewarded by other satisfaction variables (product, price, service and support system, trust). Therefore the result of analyzing customer satisfaction variables in the sight of the customers' opinions is very significant in this process. Customer's satisfaction is based on; Product, Price, Website Quality, Service & support system. However in this research the result of reliability indicates that the independent variables (product, price, website, service, trust) and dependent variable customer satisfaction have the high reliability individually that is more than 0.7 base level and the overall reliability of these variables is 0.948 that is the strongest reliability and that is positive and reliable result. Furthermore the factor analysis result shows that the KMO result of all variables is more than 0.6 and that information is sensible for execution of variable investigation. As, for every one of them KMO is greater than 0.6 and noteworthy Bartlett's test is smaller than critical level which is 0.05, that demonstrate connection network having huge data. and finally the results of regression analysis specify that product, price, website, service, trust and satisfaction of customer are powerfully connected to each other, and the correlation between all the variables have near the 1 and more than the 0.5 that is the strong relation between these variables.

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